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ROLE OF ANIMAL HUSBANDRY AND HOUSEHOLD INDUSTRIES IN DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL ECONOMY IN MAHARASHTRA

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ABSTRACT

India lives in its villages which number 638596 and contain 67.97 per cent of total population in 2013. The development of rural areas has been given an important place in the Five-Year plans. Apart from the development of agriculture, steps have been taken for the development of non-agricultural sectors of economy and provision of basic amenities for all villages within a reasonable period. This minimum needs programme seeks to provide protected water-supply, health facilities, education, electrification, link roads and house sites for weaker sections. Special emphasis is being given for villages in remote area. District Rural Development Agency has traditionally been the principal organ at the district level to oversee the implementation of the anti-poverty programmes of the ministry. The progress of the rural economy depends as much on agriculture as on non-agricultural sectors. The non-farm income is an important component of income in rural area

Cattle and buffaloes play an important role in all agricultural activities such as ploughing, transport of manure of agricultural products to market,

etc. Animal husbandry is an auxiliary activity of Indian agriculture contributing significantly to rural economy by providing rich supplementary diet and source of many raw materials for earning additional income. Household industries or cottage industry signifies those manufacturing occupations which are pursued primarily within the confines of the rural households. This industry is of immense importance to rural as well as national economy, contributing as much as 26% of total industrial production.

Keywords: Electrification, national economy, auxiliary activity, domestication

Introduction:

Animal husbandry, dairy and fisheries are allied activities to agriculture, which supplement farm income by generating gainful employment, resulting in growth of rural economy. According to 19th Livestock Census, the total livestock in the State was about 325 lakh less by 9.7 per cent compared to 18th Livestock Census. Similarly livestock per lakh population was 28,518 in 2012 less by 23.2 per cent compared to 2007. The State ranks sixth in livestock and third in poultry population. The poultry population is about 7.77 lakh which is 11 per cent of the total poultry population in India. Household industry was defined as an industry conducted by the head of the household himself/herself and/or by the members of the household at home or within the village in rural areas, and only within the precincts of the house where the household lived in urban areas. The larger proportion of workers in a household industry should consist of members of the household including the head. The industry should not be run on the scale of a registered factory. A household industry is one that is engaged in production, processing, servicing, repairing or making and selling (but not merely selling) of goods.

Objectives:

The main objectives of this paper are as follows-

1. To find out the contribution of animal husbandry in development of rural economy in Maharashtra.
2. To study the spatial distribution of animal in Maharashtra.
3. To find out the contribution of household industry in rural economy in study region.

Study Area:

Maharashtra state has been selected as per study which located in western India. Maharashtra state bounded by 15044' N to 22006'N latitudes and 72003'E to 80054'E longitudes. The total geographical area of Maharashtra state is 307713 sq.kms. divided into six division. As per 2011 census the total population accounts 11,23,72,972. This gives it a ranking of 2nd in India. Maharashtra occupies the western and central part of the country and has a long coastline stretching nearly 720 kilometers along the Arabian Sea. One of the more prominent physical features of Maharashtra is the Deccan plateau, which is separated from the Konkan coastline by 'Ghats'. Maharashtra is the third largest state by area in India. Its coastline is 330 miles (530 km) long along the Arabian Sea. The Western Ghats better known as Sahyadri, are a hilly range running parallel to the coast, at an average elevation of 1,200 metres (4,000 ft). Kalsubai, a peak in the Sahyadris, near Nashik city is the highest elevated point in Maharashtra. To the west of these hills lie the Konkan coastal plains, 50-80 kilometres in width. To the east of the Ghats lies the flat Deccan Plateau. Forests comprise 17% of the total area of the state. A majority of the forests are in the eastern and Sahyadri regions of the state.

Maharashtra is divided into five geographic regions. Konkan is the western coastal region, Kandesh is the north-western region lying in the valley of the Tapti River, Desh is in the centre of the state. Marathwada which was a part of the princely state of Hyderabad until 1956 is located in the southeastern part of the state. Vidarbha is the easternmost region of the state, formerly part of Central Provinces and Berar. Maharashtra has typical monsoon climate, with hot, rainy and cold weather seasons. However, dew, frost and hail also occur sometimes, depending upon the seasonal weather. The winter in January and February is followed by summer between March and May and the monsoon season between June and September. Temperature varies between 22 °C and 39 °C during this season. Rainfall starts normally in the first week of June. July is the wettest month in Maharashtra, while August also gets substantial rain. Monsoon starts its retreat with the coming of September to the state. Rainfall in Maharashtra differs from region to region. Thane, Raigad, Ratnagiri and Sindhudurg districts, receive heavy rains of an average of 200 centimetres annually. But the districts of Nasik, Pune, Ahmednagar, Dhule, Jalgaon,

Satara, Sangli, Solapur and parts of Kolhapur get rainfall less than 50 centimetres. Rainfall particularly concentrates at the Konkan and Sahyadrian Maharashtra. Central Maharashtra receives less rainfall.

Map No.1

Data base and Methodology:

This study completed based on secondary source of data. Secondary data obtained from daily news paper, Office of the Commissioner of Animal Husbandry, GoM,

Maharashtra Animal and Fishery Science University.

Explanation:

Animal husbandry refers to domestication of animals to obtain animal products like milk, meat, wool, Skin etc. and to use them for draught and transportation. India has a rich variety of livestock which are hardy and can withstand inadequate level of nutrition. But in Maharashtra there is variety of animal husbandry.

1. Cattle and Buffalo:

Indian has about 20% of world's cattle and half o world's buffalows population. These animals are the backbone of country's agriculture. Oxen and he-buffalows are useful in farms for ploughing, irrigating, threshing and transporting farm products to the manure and domestic fuel. These are also good source of hides and skins for leather industry which creates employment opportunities and earns substantial foreign exchange.

Table No.1 Maharashtra State Livestock as per 19th Census (000)

Sr. No.	Veterinary Region	Cattle	Buffaloes	Sheep and goats	Other livestock	Total livestock
1	Kokan	1106	397	365	16	1884
2	Nashik	3688	889	3268	126	7971
3	Pune	2488	2202	2913	56	7659
4	Aurangabad	1936	510	1163	59	3668
5	Latur	1642	683	781	39	3145
6	Amaravati	2248	453	1338	44	4083
7	Nagpur	2375	461	1188	54	4078

Source: Office of the Commissioner of Animal Husbandry, GoM

Cows and buffallow provide nutritious milk which apart from enriching the diet of rural folk provide them a substantial source of income. Owners get remunerative income by selling their milk and milk products to urban area. It is development of these animal resources which has resulted into phenomenal increase in milk production, termed as

'white Revolution leading India to become the largest milk producer in the world. Operation flood was launched in three phases that comprised National Dairy Development Programmes which include the development of infrastructure facilities for the procurement of milk from rural areas, its marketing, animal health care facilities etc. the programme has made a sound impact on rural masses, encouraging them to take up dairying as a subsidiary occupation which offers a regular source of income. More than 62% of milk procurement in the operation flood areas has come from the small, marginal and landless farmers. The rural co-operative societies have played a pivotal role in the white Revolution, the classic example being Amul, Gujarat. Amul model co-operatives are being promoted to cover about 60% of country's area.

According to 1992 livestock census there were 204.5 million cattle and 842 lakh buffaloes to all the three categories-milch breed, draught breed and dual purpose breeds. Besides milk, large quantity of farm manure becomes available and is used for generating bio-gas in rural areas to meet part of their energy demands. For example, in Kheda, Gujarat, a number of talukas have complete bio-gas facilities.

2. Sheep and goats:

Sheep are an important source of wool and mutton in the country. Sheep rearing plays an important role in the country's economy especially the rural one providing sustenance to about 5 million households. Both quality and quantity of wool and meat is low, hence efforts are being made to improve sheep breeds. A central sheep breeding farm has been established at Hissar. Approximately 92500 families are depending upon sheep rearing business. Sheep rearing is done in dry climatic districts such Pune, Satara, Solapur, Sangli, Kolhapur, Ahmednagar, Nashik, Dhule, Jalgaon, Aurangabad, Jalna, Beed, Latur, Nanded, Osmanabad, Buldhana, Chandrapur etc. In goat rearing, approximately 45 lakhs families are engaged. Both the business is carried out by weaker sections of the society.

As per statistical Report Dept. of Animal Husbandry, Maharashtra State for the maximum numbers of family engaged in these activities. Goat called poor man's cow, they provide milk, skin, hair and meat (35% of countries total meat). Some part of Maharashtra region provides Pashmina wool, which is famous for Angara breed.

3. Pig Rearing:

It plays a great role in improving socio-economic condition of the lower section (called Dalits) of rural society. It provides cheap meat rich in protein. Pig rearing is common in some part of Maharashtra. Now days the demand of this sector now decreasing due to some financial problem in Maharashtra.

4. Poultry:

About 1.2 lakhs households are being benefited through this occupation yielding 1300 crores of income annually. Besides improving the nutritional value of people's diet it generates 2.3 million tones of rich manure. Poultry has the highest rate of growth in the agricultural sector in India (8-10% in eggs, 15-20% in broilers) Poultry activities in the State are mainly operated by private poultry owners. The National Institute of Nutrition has recommended per capita per annum consumption of 180 eggs and 11 kg of poultry meat. Considering the growth potential in this sector, the State has decided to promote poultry activity through Navinyapurna Yojana and Rastriya Krishi Vikas Yojana (RKVY). During 2013-14, an expenditure of ₹ 16.10 crore and 22.95 crore was incurred under navinyapurna yojana and RKVY respectively covering 3,170 beneficiaries. Number of poultry birds supplied through central hatcheries and availability of eggs are given below.

Table No.2 Maharashtra State

Sr. No.	Year	No of poultry birds supplied (in lakhs)	Availability of eggs (per capita per annum)	
			State	All India
1	2010-11	3.87	38	53
2	2011-12	8.84	39	55
3	2012-13	8.68	40	57
4	2013-14	9.87	41	58

Source: Office of the Commissioner of Animal Husbandry, GoM

5. Sericulture:

Sericulture has potential to generate employment opportunities in rural areas. It is the cultivation of silk through rearing of silk worms involving raising of mulberry plants for

silkworms, rearing of silkworms for production of cocoons, reeling and spinning of cocoons for production of yarn etc. for value added benefits such as processing and weaving. Mulberry silk development programme is implemented in 24 districts of the State. During 2013-14, area under mulberry plantation was 1,488.10 hect less by 15.2 per cent while production of raw silk was 111.52 MT which was more by 27.5 per cent over 2012-13. During 2014-15, upto January, production of raw silk was 149.60 MT. During 2014-15 upto January, employment of 34.81 lakh mandays was generated as against 18.67 lakh mandays during the same period of the previous year.

This occupation gives part time or whole time employment to about 52 lakhs persons, mostly in the rural areas of which 40% belong to SC/ST. India is the second largest producer of the silk in the world after China. There has been tenfold increase in the production of silk between 1960-61 to 1997-98. The earning from export of silk rose from Rs. 719 crore in 1993-94 to 900 crore in 1995-96.

6. Apiculture:

It has immense potential for supplementing farmer's income and providing employment to rural youth. The country has potentiality of producing about 1.5 to 2 lakh tones of honey annually. Most of honey produced in India is collected by tribes, so it can become a major tool for improving their socio-economic condition. To promote apiculture in rural area, the government has established training and research centres in different parts of country as well as Maharashtra.

7. Pisciculture:

It helps in augmenting food supply, generating employment, raising nutritional level and earning valuable foreign exchange. It provides substance to over one million persons. Indian continental shelf area spreading over 3.1 lakh square km. area has potential of 10 million tonnes of fish annually. Similarly inland water bodies are capable of producing another 10 lakh tonnes of fish annually. The phenomenal increase in production of fishes is called Blue Revolution, though the greatest beneficiary has been the aqua culture.

8. Household Industry:

Household industries or cottage industry signifies those manufacturing occupations which are pursued primarily within the confines of the rural households. This industry is of

immense importance to rural as well as national economy, contributing as much as 16% of total industrial production.

The significance of this industry is that neither hired labour is required for heavy investment. The industry is benefited by traditional cheap technology, skills evolved over generations of experience and total raw material. It is estimated that about 25 million people are employed in these industries on a full time or part time basis. They help stabilise rural incomes especially during the lean season. Realising its importance development and co-operative units has been formed.

Most important among there is Handloom sector, providing employment to million of people. Household industries include a wide range in industries such as weaving, khadi, vegetable oil by Ghani, tanning of leather, guar and khandsari, cottage match-making, sericulture, coir, bedee making handi crafts n woods metals and in ivory etc.

Problems of animal husbandry and household industry:

There is great prospect in animal husbandry in improving the socio-economic conditions of rural masses but poor animal health care services, unscientific and unhygienic conditions of production, inadequate and low quality of fodder, poor indigenous breeds and lack of proper storage and marketing facilities are certain constraints which have to be overcome for utilizing its full potential. Presently, the contribution of livestock and fisheries sector to country's GDP was 6.8% in 2001-02 but now it is increased. The value of output of livestock and fisheries sector is about 27.7% of the total value of output from agriculture and allied sectors. Livestock sector provides regular employment to about 11 million in principal status and 8 million in subsidiary status. Women constitute 69% of the labour force in the livestock sector.

Conclusion:

1. The Government of Maharashtra created infrastructure facilities to provide health care to livestock in the state. In this state 33 district artificial insemination centres, 35 polyclinics, 168 mini polyclinics and 65 mobile veterinary clinics.
2. The state provides medical facilities for various diseases and also implements vaccination programmes. In Maharashtra 9669 general treatments are provided in 2014-15.

3. In Maharashtra livestock insurance is a centrally sponsored scheme implemented by MLDB since 2006-07. The main objective of this scheme is to provide protection to the cattle holders against any eventual losses due to death of animal because of natural calamity, accident or disease.
4. The State ranks seventh in India in milk production. Under RKVY, 46 integrated dairy farm projects are completed in 23 districts and an amount of ₹ 2,16 crore is utilised.
5. During 2013-14, there were 108 milk processing plants and 118 chilling centres with capacity of 45.31 lakh litres and 30.79 lakh litres per day respectively under government and co-operative sectors together. The average daily collection of milk by the government and co-operative dairies taken together was 39.19 lakh litres during 2013-14 and 43.33 lakh litres during 2014-15. There are 194 cold storage centres with capacity of 6,115 MT, of which 170 cold storage centres with capacity of 5,550.5 MT are with private sector.
6. During 2013-14, share of Fisheries in GSDP was 0.3 per cent. During 2013-14, State's contribution in marine, inland and total fish production of India was 13.6 per cent, 2.2 per cent and 6.3 per cent respectively. There are 173 fish landing centres on the coastline of the State. The State has 28 fish seed production centres and during 2013-14, about 1,875 crore fish seed were produced. There are 14,863 marine fishing boats in operation, of which 12,240 are mechanized.
7. Tasar silk development programme is implemented in four districts viz. Gadchiroli, Chandrapur, Bhandara and Gondia. Area under plantation of Ain and Arjun trees (on which Tasar silkworms are grown) is 18,866 ha in these four districts. During 2013-14, production of raw Tasar silk was 10.20 MT. During 2014-15 upto January, 5.28 MT raw Tasar silk was produced.
8. In Maharashtra maximum number of persons is engaged in household industries but there contribution is very low. Which families are poor only this family engaged in this activity.

References

1. Animal Husbandry and Dairying, Fisheries and Horticulture, National Planning Committee Report, Bombay, 1948, p. 17
2. Annual Report of Animal husbandry, 2013-14.
3. Birner, R. (1999). The Role of Livestock in Agricultural Development: Theoretical approaches and their application in the case of Sri Lanka. Aldershot: Ashgate.
4. Economic Survey of Maharashtra 2014-15
5. Grigg, D. (1993). The Role of Livestock in World Food Consumption. Scottish Geographical Magazine, 109(2) 66-79
6. Khan, Netal 2008: Livestock Revolution in Monsoon Asia during Post Economic Reform Period, Asian Profile, Vol. 36 No. 5, PP 529-544
7. Office of commissioner of Animal Husbandry, GoM
8. P.S.Chavan, A.S.Khose & B.G.Nair : Economic Analysis of Goat Rearing in Amravati District Vol.6 No.1, page-6-11.

लेखकांसाठी महत्त्वाच्या सुचना

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